

F.O.O.D - Food Ordering Online Desk

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ABSTRACT

In today's life everyone is busy and wants to save their time as much as possible. In weekends many people want to spend their days and evenings somewhere out from their home, but in weekends crowd are generally much more than usual days and hence it leads to wait for a long time. Even for taking parcel we have to wait for a longer time. Getting table and waiting for food after ordering will become a headache and create a challenging environment for managers of restaurants and hotels. If fortunately, we got table then we get bind to that restaurant's menu and items only whether we like it or not.

In colleges staffs are provided with coupons which is used as to-ken in canteen, but sometime it may be lost or tempered. It is also a very time-consuming process for staff members and canteen management as well.

Now we are coming with a great application with some interesting ideas and ingredients. It helps to reduce the time, efforts, and resources for both vendors (Hotels and restaurants) and customers. Through this application we may able to pre-order our food, and will be able to view waiting period of table availability at that particular restaurant. Customers can select through choices of their food or restaurants nearby them, which will give them a large amount of flexibility and options to worth their time spending at that place.

INTRODUCTION

With the online food ordering method, food is ordered online and delivered to the customer. This is made possible through the use of electronic payment

system. The payment can be done through the customer's credit card, debit card. So, in this project we design a system which will allow customers to go online and place order for their food. Due to the rapid growth in the use of internet and the technologies associated with it, the several opportunities are coming up on the web. So many businesses and companies are now undertaking into their business with comfort be- cause of the internet. One of the businesses that the internet introduced is an online food ordering system. In today's life many restaurants have focus on quick preparation and speedy delivery of orders rather than offering a rich dining experience. Recently, most of this delivery orders were placed over the phone, but there are many drawbacks of this system.

It is possible for everyone to order any goods from anywhere via the internet and have the goods delivered at his/her home. But while trying to discuss the transfer method of the goods and services, attention is focused on the payment mode. In other words, how possible is it to pay for goods and services via the internet? This then leads to the discussion of the economic consequences of digital cash. What are the implementations from the view point of economic? Since the world is fast becoming a global village, the necessary tool for this process is communication of which telecommunication is a key player? A major breakthrough is the wireless 2 telephone system which comes in either fixed wireless telephone lines or the Global System of Mobile communication (GSM).

Online ordering system is originally designed for use in college cafeterias, but just as applicable in any

food delivery industry. The main advantage of this system is that it greatly simplifies the ordering process for both the customer and the restaurant. By making entire process of taking orders is automatically the load on restaurants end is lightened. Once an order is placed on the webpage that will be designed, it is placed into the database and then retrieved, in pretty much real-time, by a desktop application on the restaurants end. Within this application, all items in the order are displayed, along with their corresponding options and delivery details, in a concise and easy to read manner. This allows the restaurant employees to quickly go through the orders as they are placed and produce the necessary items with minimal delay and confusion. The greatest advantage of this system is its FLEXIBILITY.

LITERATURE SURVEY

Pre-cooked food leads to wastage of food if less number of customer visited. When customer visits to restaurants they have to wait 15-20 min to get their orders. Sometimes food taste and Quality may do not match with requirement of customers but they take orders from restaurants because of no previous knowledge. Food panda, zomato, etc. applications are already exist but they are providing home delivery services from nearest restaurants and food courts only. In order to reduce service cost and enhance customer experiences, few restaurants have invested in the service automation system. The automation system used to capture the food order from guests ranged in many forms but mostly comprise of an electronic device with a screen presenting the menu and accept user's input for order placing First waiter takes the order from customer. After taking the order, waiter should enter that order in system where PC was set up. At the kitchen information was displayed on screen. The kitchen staff would then prepare the dishes according to order and after completion of order they would inform to waiter, who collected and delivered the dishes to the respective tables. The system was also informing the waiter about the availability of a dish. If a certain dish was not available then waiter was able to ask for changes or even cancel a customer's order. After serving the order, bill was generated at

the cash counter as per customer order. The management had full authority to access all details of the customer which are fed into the system. Some zigbee based ordering systems are also present. These systems use zigbee module for communication purposes. Zigbee technology is preferred for node to node communications.

SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

It comprises four distinct component subsystems, each of which implements the following functionalities, respectively: Validation of Users, Order Placing, Location and waiting time management, feedback and Rating. These activities are integrated together to form the overall F.O.O.D system.

- 1) Validation of Users: In this all user (Including Hotels Owner and Customers) validation will done. This module will include 5 sub modules: Login, registration, forget password, reset password, email and mobile no verification (using mail and OTP respectively). This user details will be saved in Database.
- 2) Order Placing: In this module User can see list of items and prices. And can place order to any hotel listed in system. In this user can sort using given rating. This module includes 2 main sub modules ordering food, bill paying (using online account or from wallets).
- 3) Location And waiting time Management: In this module main focus will be waiting time. This waiting time will be dependent on present crowd in restaurant, this module includes two sub modules waiting time management and location system. This waiting will be improved(reduced) by location system. Far distance customer can take some more time to reach restaurant so system can reduce time or reduce waiting time for nearer customer

- 4) Feedback and Rating: This module includes two sub modules: feedback system and rating system. After placing order if not received or successfully receive order, then customer can give feedback and rating. This will help future customer to choose better things

METHODOLOGY

Here customer first registers his/her details to the website or application. A login screen for entering the username, password will be provided. Access to different screens will be based upon the user. There is a screen for placing order as per choice. There is screen for billing of order and for changing profiles information regarding personal information. There is a screen for getting order as per orders made by user for that hotel. there is screen for changing menu and price regarding hotel customization. There is a screen for owners for displaying information regarding orders to be made by user. If the user entered wrong username and password the message will be displayed that the username and password are invalid. If account does not exist then the message would be displayed that the account is not exist. Users should be comfortable with the English language. Users should have prior information regarding the online examinations. Users should have basic knowledge and should be comfortable using general purpose applications on computers..

CONCLUSION

In this paper we are providing information of online ordering of food. This application will lead to select the proper place for enjoying your food/meal with great quality and services. This will also helpful for reducing wastage of time and food for users and vendors as well.

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